

The early history of Kilvey Woods

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Alongside Hafod, Swansea's White Rock copper works is probably the most famous industrial history site we have, although very little survives above ground to give any sense to the two centuries of industrial activity that happened there. I know the site well, having grown up locally and commuted by foot, bicycle, and car past White Rock for nearly 30 years. I fondly remember early morning encounters with rabbits and afternoon spotting of reptiles as I walked along what was the railway track until the landscaping of the 1990s.

The industrial archaeology of White Rock is well-known and thoroughly documented.¹ Many lament the 1960s destruction that removed so many of the existing remains, and looking at the site today, it is impossible to envisage the dense clusters of industrial buildings that were crammed into that bend of the Tawe.² White Rock's proximity to the slopes of Kilvey Hill meant that the Hill was profoundly affected by every activity in the works, whether it be water extraction, coal mining, smoke pollution, and most importantly, waste tipping. Outside of the Hafod chimneys, the most visible legacies of Swansea's copper industry nowadays are Kilvey's woodlands but also the landscape scars that still lie beneath them. Industrial heritage has often been a challenging 'sell' to a modern post-industrial world. More so in a Swansea that can lay claim to being one of the world's earliest industrial areas with industrial archaeology throughout much of the subsurface of our urban area.³ Recognising and dealing with industrial heritage (good and bad) is a European challenge as much as a Swansea one.⁴ However, the pioneering work of the Lower Swansea Valley Project in the 1960s has assured Swansea of a prominent place in the history of environmental reconstruction and repair.⁵ A role perhaps even more significant in the new circumstances of climate change. In a quite insightful section, the 2012 re-evaluation of the surviving Hafod ruins and their reinterpretation as a heritage park acknowledged the role of the 'icon' of Kilvey Hill and its regeneration as part of the industrial heritage of the wider area.⁶ The extent of clearance in Swansea has ruled out the establishment of a World Heritage Site in similar style to Blaenavon, although the green core of the Lower Swansea Valley and Kilvey will likely be of more local benefit to biodiversity, environment, and community than the bleaker landscapes of the heritage iron or slate industries.⁷

Conventionally, in the history of the White Rock site, much is made of its location, near a navigable river, easy access to coal, and engineered access to waterpower. Eventually, coal became doubly important as steam engines were introduced first as support for the water-powered infrastructure and eventually to replace waterpower.⁸ Less often mentioned, outside primary sources, is the need for land for tips. Tipping is a vital part of the smelting process, and a significant part of the White Rock story. The landscape we have today is the combination of a remarkable industry working for two centuries in a highly constrained geographical location. Aside from the industrial processes running on the site, it was the physical location that focussed the negative effects of the smoke and waste pollution on the surrounding landscape and eventually resulting in the woodlands we have today.

This study looks at the landscape adjoining the works. Changing the focus and dropping the industrial remains out of the picture reveals interesting history and lessons for the future. Despite the industrial devastation and the upheavals of the post-industrial phase, there are remarkable survivals of the eighteenth-century landscape which have escaped notice over the past decades. This is understandable, the star of the show was often the White Rock ruins or the regret over the loss of them (mainly destroyed 1963-5).⁹ The early 1970s were a frenzy of remediation and Forestry Commission planting to hide the landscape scars. The bridge and road junction remodelling of the 1990s finally removed many surface features that survived. However, that is far from the end of the story, the history of environmental restoration and repair may be the best story of all.

Figure 1 An extract from the 1744 drawing of White Rock. The artist was viewing from Hafod on the west bank. The works is shown in detail on the right. Nestling amongst the trees centre left is Ty Cnap Goch, the most prominent location on the coal road. The arti

The early 1700s

The industrial development of the White Rock site was chronicled in the early 1980s.¹⁰ Key sources for the early history of the site are scarce with just two copy leases from c. 1736, and 1805.¹¹ Despite being such a significant site, the chronology of the early sources is slightly unclear. The document described as a lease by R.O. Roberts is only an abstracted copy of the lease which is not clear on its precise dating. An Abstract of Lease is an office copy of the original document, usually to provide the legal information in a paper copy, they can often be lacking in key details such as dates and parties to the document. The contents of the Abstract suggest that the Mansel Estates were keen to encourage a coal-using enterprise on the site of an old grist mill as a market for coal coming down the valley. Mansel Estates coal was already being transported to and shipped from Mansel's White Rock coal yard on the riverside. Discussions with suitable Bristol-based entrepreneurs resulted in an Agreement For Sale on 24 August 1735 and a lease dated on or before 1 November 1735 with a term commencement date of 25 March 1737 for 51 years. Many other short-term leases followed in later years. Occupation of the land by the leaseholders began on or around March 1737. R.O. Roberts' original analysis of the document understandably concentrates on the development of the copper works itself, but a re-reading for landscape history gives some extra insights.

In the 1730s, the site was already occupied and busy, there was rich agricultural saltmarsh (Morfa Carw), a busy tramroad down to the Mansel coal yard (the original 'White Rock') and there was a large watermill with a millpond. The mill was described as an '*old decayed or ruinous Water Corn Grist Mill called Knaploth Mill*' (a corruption of Craig Cnap Coch or similar)¹². There was also provision for demolition of the Mill as:

*'...free liberty to pull down and destroy the said Mill and to erect and build in the stead thereof any other Mill or Mills Engines or other devices whatsoever if wanted or necessary for the use of the said intended Works.'*¹³

This is confirmation the site had a waterpower resource from Kilvey Hill, and it was intended from the outset to adapt what existed to supply waterpower to the site. Generally, across the town, almost all suitable waterpower sites in Swansea had some mill activity at some point in pre-industrial times. The Knaploth Mill survived long enough to be included in a drawing of White Rock dated 1744 by Thomas Lightfoot and shown as a substantial building in

front of an impressive millpond, with a tantalising view of the main feeder stream and valley winding up Kilvey Hill.¹⁴ Sadly, the stream does not have a name that has survived, although I have called it Nant Llwynheirnin in my mapping in reference to the area on the Hill near Llwynheirnin Farm and Coal Pits where it originated before the substantial alterations to the stream structure in the 1740s.

It is difficult to estimate when the mill was demolished. The vigorous growth of the White Rock works in the late 1700s must have meant the building was removed and the material recycled into the numerous buildings within the works by the early 1800s at the latest. The millpond was more durable and survived as a substantial structure to be mapped on the 1879 edition of the 1:500 OS plan.¹⁵ It is possible that the pond served some useful purpose in the works as it would surely have been removed earlier being in a central location on such a cramped and confined industrial site.

The existence of the millpond raised an interesting question about the availability of water. Where did the water come from that fed the millpond and eventually the water powered hammers ('the battery') in the White Rock works? The original mill was built on the course of the large stream (Nant Llwynheirnin) that ran in a valley down the slope of Kilvey Hill. The steep valley supplied a significant head of water that flowed fast down the Hill and either supplied the mill's waterwheels directly or in later years, fed the mill pond which allowed for greater control over water use. Originally, the stream drained a large part of the north-western side of the Hill. The stream valley survives as a significant feature, of which more later.

The Nant Llwynheirnin was not just the source of water for the old mill. It quickly became incorporated into the wider waterpower network for the area which had been created to service the considerable coal mining industry of early industrial Swansea. The importance of waterpower in the coal industry has been thoroughly examined over the past thirty years and tracing the numerous leats and channels across Swansea can be an absorbing task for a local historian.¹⁶

The 1730s Abstract referred to above confirms that the availability of waterpower, and the ability to improve quantity and quality was an important incentive to make the White Rock site attractive to potential tenants. The Abstract has three key waterpower clauses safeguarding water supply from the mainstream (Nant Llwynheirnin) and a network of leats covering the western side of the Hill. The Mansel Estate was certainly keen to encourage the development by making it easy for Thomas Coster and his Bristol partners to exploit as much waterpower as possible from Kilvey.

The original lease was drafted in a time when maps or plans were scarce and so the lands of Kilvey are described by placename only. The Mansel Estate offered water resources from Llanerch, Craig Tyle Brown, Clyder Melyn y Wrane, with a final catch-all of any other Mansel lands. Potentially this was almost all the western side of Kilvey, and future developments show people went to a lot of trouble to improve the water flow into the sluice of Knaploth Millpond. Typically, the drafting clerk was unfamiliar with Welsh language and struggled to spell out the names accurately, so spelling can be variable. The placenames confirm that the northern slopes of Kilvey were channelled to supply extra water into the Nant Llwynheirnin.¹⁷

For the early White Rock works, the key part of the waterpower infrastructure, in 1735 and what it would eventually become in the century after, was the channel or sluice into the Knaploth Millpond. It was also something that once established, would be hard to alter. This last point may be why the Nant Llwynheirnin inlet into the White Rock site was (and still is) a permanent fixture. The sluice survives as it was built to carry the water under the Turnpike Road and onto the White Rock site. Currently it carries the much-reduced stream remnant under the Pentrechwyth road (the old Turnpike), the A4217, and into the White Rock heritage site. Then, it travels south in various tunnels to run over the little aqueduct at the mouth of the Smiths Canal tunnel and into the river. The survival of the sluice is remarkable given the upheavals to the landscape in the area since the 1920s. The plan evidence we have shows that the stream ran in a tunnel under the Turnpike and then in an open channel into the White Rock site. The structure was clearly mapped in 1879 on the 1:500 town plan although its brick arch construction suggests an earlier date. The open channel survived into the 1880s on various OS plans although it is now firmly submerged beneath the modern roads.¹⁸

Figure 2 The surviving White Rock stream sluice that originally fed the hammer pond and probably the millpond before the 1730s.

The Abstract's water clauses point to something else that was happening. The provision to allow enhancement and development of the waterpower running into the site via Nant Llwynheiernin suggests both forward thinking and concern over water resources. The northern watercourse used to supplement the Knaploth Mill has already been mentioned, however, the 1740s saw a lot more activity to enhance the water supply of Nant Llwynheiernin by an elaborate series of water engineering developments south of the Nant to intercept water from streams running down the southwest of Kilvey into Foxhole and channel into the Nant to feed that all important sluice mentioned above. Waterpower in early industry inherited all the worries and risks of the grain and wool industries. Winter freezing and summer droughts could paralyse water-powered activities and even damage the wheels and equipment. Kilvey may have had an additional risk with intensive coal mining affecting the water table of the north and western side of the Hill. It is possible that extra water supplies were sought to provide more reliable and regular water supply for the White Rock hammers. And there is also an insurance clause to allow the leaseholders to relocate their hammers to a more reliable waterpower site upriver from White Rock nearer Llansamlet.¹⁹ I'll discuss the network of leats later.

Although the creation of more water channels and leats had a significant effect on the land, it was the tipping of industrial waste that profoundly affected what we see today. Copper production was a noxious and toxic industry, and it transformed the landscape. The air pollution saga that dominated the civic affairs of Swansea in the 1820s and 1830s is nationally famous and comprehensively documented.²⁰ More enduring are the physical waste piles the industry produced. Recent figures suggest that each tonne of copper in the 1730s could have generated approximately twenty-six tonnes of waste, although I constantly wonder if that is an underestimate.²¹ The 1730s Abstract has three substantial clauses ensuring provision for space for dumping of waste. This is where the physical geography of the site becomes of crucial importance. The original White Rock site as leased in 1735 was barely more

than 2.4 hectares (6 acres), which left about two hectares (c. 4.5 acres) of adjoining fields and saltmarsh (known as Cae Morfa Carw) for tipping of smelting waste. The fields adjoined a larger enclosure to the north (Morfa Carw) which was owned by the Duke of Beaufort. This northern enclosure would eventually become Middle Bank Works. A lot of the land was only just above sea level, and the land adjoining the river was stone shoals, salt marsh, and pasture. Nowadays, most of the urban reach of the river has been embanked or hidden under a barrage, but a flavour of the original character of the river where it passed Morfa Carw and White Rock, can be gained by looking at the reach of the river at the 2014 flood scheme near Ynys Forgan.

Figure 3 When left to its own devices the river quickly reverts to a close approximation of its original form. Here are the stony banks reappearing after the 2014 flood prevention works at Ynysforgan. The 1730s Hafod and Cae Carw looked a lot like this

The B. Jones 1771 plan of the river gives the best indication of the extent of saltmarsh along the banks of both Hafod and Morfa Carw.²² Although the 1730s river was described as ‘navigable’ up to Morfa Quay, the usable channel must have been extremely narrow and subject to disruption by the vagaries of the river. In places, the channel looks to be 10m or less wide. The Jones’ map does not give us much of a view of what is on Morfa Carw, but the Thomas Lightfoot drawing mentioned earlier and dating from the 1740s, gives a vivid impression of the salt marsh fringing the river with grazing animals, and the meadows behind. Lightfoot has recorded the grassland and hedgerows being steadily submerged beneath the advancing piles of slag coming from the southern side. Ominously, the artist has even depicted a series of dead trees, likely casualties of the early pollution. The existence of the ‘marsh’ has been slightly obscured over the years by the misinterpretation by George Grant Francis and others of the caption to Lightfoot’s drawing as the ‘Mount’ rather than the ‘Marsh’.²³

The land surface we have today at White Rock is about 4m higher than the fields of Morfa Carw, but this is because the landscaping of the 1990s levelled out a lot of the small mountain of waste that marked the location of the original Cae Morfa Carw. The works did not level it all out, the central hill of waste at the centre of the White Rock Heritage Park is a lasting gravestone over the ancient meadow.

Even though the 1735 lease made provision for using the Morfa Carw meadows as a tip, all parties knew that was not going to be enough. There was obviously a concern that slag was going to end up being tipped into the river or at least migrating out from the tips created on the meadows, which would have made that narrow navigable channel even more difficult. To try and prevent that happening, the lease had a rather weakly worded clause to prevent slag and ash being thrown into the river to “*prejudice the navigation of the River Tawy*”.²⁴ Over the years, this seems to have had limited effect and a sketch of White Rock from the end of the 1700s clearly shows waste tips in contact with the river and having engulfed the whole of Cae Morfa Carw.²⁵ The other insurance offered was to allow tipping of waste on adjoining Mansel lands which can only have meant the land around Cnap Goch House north of the White Rock site. The road to that tipping site was well established and Ty Knap Coch and its surrounding land were prominent on the Lightfoot drawing in 1744, the road being an important route for coal traffic coming from the Mansel Estates down to the Mansel Coal Yard at White Rock Quay. As this was quite an uphill slope, it is likely that tipping there was a choice only taken when space on Cae Morfa Carw had run out, possibly by the early 1800s. By the 1820s most of the Lower Swansea Valley industries were building inclined planes to deal with the mountains of waste coming from the smelters.²⁶

Figure 4 My redrawing of part of the de Louthenberg sketch from the end of the 1700s, showing the dominance of the slag tips starting to dwarf the works.

The 1800s

The second half of the eighteenth century saw a massive increase in copper production from White Rock and the other sites in the valley. In 1809, the famous Hafod works added massively to the productivity and to the pollution.

As early as 1802, the hill above White Rock was lifeless. The pollution on the dead hillside was sufficient to be mentioned by George Grant Francis in his 1881 celebration of the Swansea copper industry.²⁷ This is surprising as Francis was clearly keen to talk up the industry in a fine example of boosterism, but it may reflect the unavoidably ugly state of the hillside as it appeared to tourists of the early 1800s.²⁸ Francis returns to the subject later in his book with reference to Hafod being ‘denuded of every vestige of verdure’, with nature last ‘having her sway’ in the 1730s.²⁹ This last being a remarkable early example of the concept of nature being swept aside by industrialisation, a concept reignited in the early 1980s.³⁰

As mentioned earlier, the waste tips had engulfed Cae Morfa Carw by the end of the nineteenth century. The de Louthenberg drawing suggests that the waste tips were getting too big for dumping by wheelbarrow and more sophisticated measures were needed to allow tipping to continue. It’s also hard to believe that the growing White

Rock tips didn't threaten the navigation of the river, particularly as the drawing shows unconsolidated waste rising up to 4-5m above the river surface on the banks of the Tawe, a river renowned for its violent flooding and flow, and tendency to transport massive quantities of debris (and probably copper waste) into the Town Reach and Fabian's Bay.³¹ The actual details of how waste was moved around the cramped White Rock site are not known to us, however the issue as it affected the adjacent Vivians works in the 1840s has been nicely summarised in some detail in recent work detailing the sheer hard manual labour of the early waste disposal part of the industry.³² The lack of space within the works probably meant intensive work with wheelbarrows in the 1730s and later, some rapid development of plateways for trams like those used in the coal industry. The evolution of cableways and inclined planes alongside better wheels and tramrails meant that methods of moving waste to the valley side became quite complex in the 1820s. The Vivian's Hafod works was experiencing similar problems with its smelting waste and had installed a steam powered winding engine by 1826 to haul waste to the top of the mountain of waste known as Pentre Hafod.³³ There was a similar arrangement at White Rock with the remnants of the inclined plane onto the Hill still forming part of the visible remains.³⁴

The growth of the tips on the Kilvey slopes poses some interesting questions. As far as I can tell, the need for waterpower for White Rock was of high importance up to the 1840s. Although there was provision in the 1805 lease for construction of a 'Fire Engine', this was clearly intended to supplement waterpower provision through the Nant Llwynheiernin ("One Fire Engine for the purpose of supplying the Stream or Watercourse by which the Machinery of the said Copper and Brass Works hereby demised have been hitherto worked with a sufficient quantity of water for that purpose").³⁵

By the time the OS 1:500 plan had been compiled in the 1870s there was a notable change.³⁶ The plan shows that, via an inclined plane, tipping had spread over a large part of the lower reach of the Nant Llwynheiernin and must have interfered with the leat and water channel system, although the drainage sluice to the original Knap Goch Millpond remained open (as it does today). The waterpower system that had evolved since mediaeval times and powered the first one hundred years of copper production finally seemed to have lost its significance.

Figure 5 Leat 4 survives as a green oasis of biodiversity as it threads through the pines in Compartment 309.

The development of inclined planes and steam winding engines from the 1820s allowed freedom from the constraint of purely manual barrow and truck-based 'slag-tramming'. The removal of constraint came at the moment of the greatest growth of the valley industries and the associated output of waste.³⁷ The adoption of steam power and tram roads allowed wider distribution of waste across the Hill and into the fields and meadows of Hafod, Landore,

and Cae Morfa. Some sentiment of the loss experienced surfaces in the witness statements from the copper smoke trials of the 1830s. Morgan Morgan testified that Kilvey was now 'barren as a road, and the meadows of Hafod and Cae Morfa had all gone.'³⁸ The OS 1:500 plan does indeed show horrifying extents of slag and waste in octopus-like tentacle shapes reflecting the meandering of tram lines dumping successive layers of waste.

By the early 1800s, the ecology of the Hill had been devastated by copper smoke. The tithe apportionment from the 1830s confirms that John Freeman or subsequent companies had acquired most Kilvey farms east of White Rock. The lack of detail on the 1830s tithe plan suggests the surveyors found little of interest to map there.³⁹ The dead land would have been regarded as fit for nothing better than dumping. By the 1870s, the Cae Morfa Carw marshes had been buried by a hectare of slag at least 4m in height and higher in parts. The riverside tip must have been physically incapable of taking any more waste by the 1820 and it does not change its shape or size in successive OS maps and surveys until the 1960s. The extent of the 'secondary tip' across the turnpike and up to Cnap Goch House had spread to at least 8 ha by 1879. The inclined plane enabled easier tipping and waste was spread up to and beyond the old house which survived as a ruin surrounded by waste until the 1880s. The tip was active reflecting the fortunes of the White Rock Works, but by 1924 the works had closed with tipping ending shortly after, by which time the tip had expanded to about 12 ha.⁴⁰ The tip continued to be worked and extracted as suitable ballast for roads and embankments up until 1967.⁴¹ Famously, a lot of the northern tip slag was used to raise the land surface for the Morganite site at the northern end of the Enterprise Zone.⁴²

The polluting phase of White Rock lasted just over 188 years. The other industries of Hafod and Landore would grow and dwarf White Rock in the profits made and also their negative environmental impact.⁴³ Slag from the valley became a near ubiquitous Swansea building and repair material. I recall coming across a slag-based repair to the eighteenth-century Cadle cornmill leat in the heart of the Llan valley, and much is made of the slag coping stones of the Trevian streets.⁴⁴ Of course, Swansea was far more than just a copper town as has been very ably discussed in recent work.⁴⁵ Swansea is a town wrought by coal mining, with lasting impacts above and below ground. Even in Penllergaer in the north of Swansea, the ongoing reconstruction of a genteel country estate, is based on land devastated by coal mining in a phase of exploitation that had ended by the 1780s, invisible in the vegetation but still plain in Lidar scans today.⁴⁶ The slag tips are sometimes less recognised in the various histories of Swansea's industry.⁴⁷ But just as industry had a profound effect on Swansea's history, the pollution left behind had (and still has) a profound effect on Swansea's geography.

Figure 6 White Rock and the Kilvey Hill area in February 1941. This is part of a series of bomb damage evaluation surveys conducted by the Luftwaffe across South Wales as part of the air war. The bomb damage assessor has identified in the white box the roofless ruins of the White

Rock works as bomb damage (a common error). The white circles are craters of other bomb hits. The bend of the river is extreme left and the dark land above the white square is the Cae Morfa Carw tip. The mass of the secondary tip is centre left sprawling over the flank of Kilvey. I don't think there is a single tree identifiable in this view. To the right of the tip at centre is the Nant Llwynheiernin valley showing signs of erosion because of the removal of protective vegetation due to the aerial pollution from the valley industries. The elaborate leat system is shown by the straight channels that cross the slopes collecting water and channelling into the Nant Llwynheiernin. The industrial hamlet of Grenfell's Town is at the top.

The history in the landscape

Nowadays, the land that formed the White Rock tips is highly regarded as either part of the industrial heritage park (what was the Cae Morfa Carw meadow), or the Kilvey woodlands. Although the Cae Morfa Carw tip is currently only landscaped and grassed, the Kilvey tip has been transformed into vibrant woodland. A generation of outdoor enthusiasts are growing up using Kilvey woodland with little or no idea of the troubled past of the land. Indeed, in walking across the hill it is sometimes hard to even comprehend the industrial past of the area.

The easy availability of Lidar data on the Welsh Governments Lle Portal is having a significant impact on local history research.⁴⁸ Alongside fieldwalking and old maps, Lidar is fast becoming a staple of research, even more so in conjunction with modern GIS applications. The industrial history discussed earlier can be followed in successive editions of the Ordnance Survey 6-inch map.⁴⁹ Naturally, the focus of history has always been on the actual ruins of White Rock with the history of the tips being a bit more challenging. The earliest useful photographs I have of the tips comes from July 1940, with later photos in February 1941. These are the photos are from the surveys of Swansea made by the German Air Force in preparation for bombing attacks. The Luftwaffe fitted their aircraft with very high-quality survey cameras which have left us superb detail of the Lower Swansea Valley area.⁵⁰ The images show the tips as massive and distinctive, so much so that they are clearly identifiable from over seven thousand metres altitude (c. twenty-five thousand feet). The large format prints show us the incredible extent of the ecological devastation of the land. The effect is even more dramatic when we combine the Luftwaffe images with Lidar surveys and Forestry Commission planting records. The Luftwaffe image extract here is from a survey mission flown over Swansea during lunchtime on 15 February 1941.⁵¹ This mission was part preparation for the heavy air raids later that week, 17-21 February 1941.⁵² One of the most striking features about this image is the almost complete lack of trees across western Kilvey, an impact of two centuries of atmospheric pollution from White Rock, Landore and Hafod. The lack of ground vegetation also shows the network of leats and watercourses created after 1740 to feed water into the Nant Llwynheiernin and onto the White Rock hammer pond. The secondary tip has covered the lower course of the Nant Llwynheiernin and its cloaking effect over the topography is dramatic. However, the sluice that collected the Nant and channelled it into White Rock is clear of debris as it still is today.

The considerable efforts to remove the tips are part of the story of the Lower Swansea Valley Project.⁵³ Although the main tip was geographically outside the scope of the Project, it was considered essential to remove what was seen as one of the most visible tips in the valley. By 1968 after about six months of work, tip material was either removed or regraded and part of the Nant Llwynheiernin valley was reinstated. The Forestry Commission completed further ploughing and land treatment in the early 1970s to plant a crop of timber trees.⁵⁴ It was this further ploughing that disrupted a lot of the land surface including removing the remains of the original pre-industrial tracks across the land. I think by that point nobody believed any original land surface or features survived, although that is clearly not the case. Walking the Hill to assess woodland health I could see that most of the original leat system survives. A fact confirmed by the Lidar record.⁵⁵ Despite the evidence of considerable stream and leat networks, nowadays a much smaller volume of water runs off the western side of Kilvey. In fact, Nant Llwynheiernin despite the size of its river valley, barely registers a trickle in winter and is largely dry the rest of the year. The same is true for the numerous leats adjoining the Nant. The hydrology and water table has changed dramatically since the early 1700s leaving dry riverbeds. This is probably an outcome of the extensive coal mining on the north and east of Kilvey draining groundwater away. The change raises another point. The extensive leat network created between the 1730s and the 1820s may have been an effort to maintain waterpower into White Rock in the face of declining water flow from the natural stream network, expanding further south to collect additional streams that would have flowed down into Foxhole. This could also explain the substantial clauses securing access to water resources in both

documents discussed earlier. There are at least five major channels above Foxhole which either connect streams or intercept water courses and channel their flow into Nant Llwynheiernin.

As mentioned earlier, the completion of the Lower Swansea Valley Project had a huge beneficial impact on western Kilvey and the restoration of woodlands in the 1970s and the later natural regeneration of vegetation are creating an environmental renaissance for the Hill. We will never be able to recreate the original woodland on the Hill, we have lost everything from that earlier time, but a combination of sensitive and thoughtful management from Swansea Council, NRW, and the local volunteer groups is creating a new type of urban Welsh woodland.

Figure 7 False colour digital terrain image of the present landscape. Mostly obscured by tree planting now. The original leat system has largely survived 1970s deep ploughing for tree planting.

¹ Stephen Hughes, *Copperopolis: Landscapes of the Early Modern Industrial Period in Swansea* (Aberystwyth: Royal Commission on the Ancient and Historical Monuments of Wales., 2000), pp. 22–30; South West Wales Industrial Archaeology Society, *Industrial Archaeology Trail of the Lower Swansea Valley* (Swansea: Swansea City Council, 1975). The Trail pamphlet is fondly remembered by many walkers who used it to discover the Lower Swansea Valley for the first time.

² Stephen Hughes, p. 329.

³ Stephen Hughes, p. vii. Describing threats to the heritage landscape in the rush of new infrastructure projects in the valley in the 1990s.

⁴ Anna Storm, *Post-Industrial Landscape Scars* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2014), chaps 1, 5.

⁵ J.R. Alban, 'Rebuilding a Future: The Reclamation of the Lower Swansea Valley Exhibition Catalogue' (Swansea City Council, 1991).

⁶ Tehmina Goskar, 'Cu @ Swansea: An Industrious Future from an Industrial Past', p. 14

<https://www.academia.edu/1969069/Cu_at_Swansea_An_industrious_future_from_an_industrial_past> [accessed 27 November 2021].

⁷ Chris Barber, *Exploring Blaenavon Industrial Landscape World Heritage Site* (Abergavenny: Blorenge Books, 2002). A beautifully readable tour through the Blaenavon World Heritage Site.

⁸ 'Copy of Lease Dated 21 September 1805', 1805, p. 14, West Glamorgan Archives Service, DD Xhr 32. See for example the clause inserted into this lease to allow the construction of a steam engine to pump more water into the Knap Goch leat or Nant Llwynheiernin to supply the White Rock Battery.

⁹ Borough Engineer, Surveyor and Planning Officer's Department, *A Report of the Reclamation of the Former Tip Complex of the White Rock Copper Works, Swansea, 1969*, West Glamorgan Archive Service, PL11/17/7.

¹⁰ R.O. Roberts, 'The White Rock Copper and Brass Works, near Swansea, 1736-1806', *Glamorgan Historian*, 12 (1981), 136–51.

¹¹ 'Abstract of Lease Dated 21 March 1736', 1736, West Glamorgan Archives Service, DD Xhr 31; 'Copy of Lease Dated 21 September 1805'.

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- ¹² (Abstract of Lease dated 21 March 1736 between 1. B Mansel 2. T Coster and others), p.2.
- ¹³ 'Abstract of Lease Dated 21 March 1736', p. 2.
- ¹⁴ George Grant Francis, *The Smelting of Copper in the Swansea District of South Wales from the Time of Elizabeth to the Present Day*, 2nd edn (London: Henry Southeran, 1881), p. 116; R.O. Roberts, p. 138.
- ¹⁵ Ordnance Survey of Wales, 'Glamorgan XXIV.1.14' (London: Ordnance Survey, 1879) <<http://hdl.handle.net/10107/4715288>>.
- ¹⁶ Stephen Hughes, pp. 103–25. A fascinating insight into the complexity of the waterpower phase of Swansea's industry.
- ¹⁷ Stephen Hughes, pp. 106–7. Confirms the existence of the leat as part of the wider network in the area.
- ¹⁸ Ordnance Survey of Wales.
- ¹⁹ 'Abstract of Lease Dated 21 March 1736', p. 9. "...and if the water which then was or Co(uld) be brought to White Rock afsd should prove insufficient to supply a Battery Mill or Trial Hammer for proving of Copper that then it should be lawful for them to have & enjoy the mill of the sd B. Mansel called the New Mill in the parish of Lansamlet afsd the remainder of the term rent free and the same to pull down and in the stead thereof to erect & build a Battery Mill or Trial Hammer for proving of Copper".
- ²⁰ Ronald Rees, *King Copper: South Wales and the Copper Trade 1584-1895* (Cardiff: University of Wales Press, 2000), chaps 4 and 5.
- ²¹ John C. Symons, 'The Mining and Smelting of Copper in England and Wales, 1760-1820' (unpublished masters, Coventry University in collaboration with University College Worcester, 2003), p. 92 <https://doi.org/10/10._Bibliography.pdf>.
- ²² William H. Jones, *History of the Port of Swansea* (Carmarthen: W. Spurrel and Son, 1922), p. 55.
- ²³ George Grant Francis, p. 117; R.O. Roberts, p. 139.
- ²⁴ 'Abstract of Lease Dated 21 March 1736', p. 7.
- ²⁵ Tate, "'A Large Copper-Smelting Works at Swansea (Perhaps the Copper Works at Landore on the River Tawe, North of Swansea)", Philip James De Louthembourg, 1786 or 1800', Tate <<https://www.tate.org.uk/art/artworks/de-louthembourg-a-large-copper-smelting-works-at-swaneasa-perhaps-the-copper-works-at-d36406>> [accessed 27 November 2021].
- ²⁶ Stephen Hughes, p. 30.
- ²⁷ George Grant Francis, pp. 115–16.
- ²⁸ David Boorman, *The Brighton of Wales* (Swansea: Swansea Little Theatre, 1986), p. 93.
- ²⁹ George Grant Francis, p. 139.
- ³⁰ Carolyn Merchant, *The Death of Nature: Women, Ecology and the Scientific Revolution* (New York: Harper and row, 1980), p. 128.
- ³¹ William H. Jones, pp. 158–67.
- ³² Chris Evans and Louise Miskell, *Swansea Copper; A Global History* (Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 2020), pp. 98–99.
- ³³ Stephen Hughes, p. 30.
- ³⁴ Stephen Hughes, p. 23.
- ³⁵ 'Copy of Lease Dated 21 September 1805', p. 14.
- ³⁶ Ordnance Survey of Wales. This series of plans at 1:500 scale covers the urban area of the town in the 1870s. Luckily, coverage extended to include mapping of the White Rock works and its waste tip
- ³⁷ Louise Miskell, *'Intelligent Town': An Urban History of Swansea, 1780-1855*, Studies in Welsh History (Cardiff: University of Wales Press, 2006), pp. 80–86.
- ³⁸ Ronald Rees, p. 78.
- ³⁹ 'Welsh Tithe Maps - Home' <<https://places.library.wales/viewer/4570048>> [accessed 27 November 2021]. The Apportionment of the Rent-Charge in lieu of Tithes in the Parish of Lansamlet, White Rock Works, p.14
- ⁴⁰ Nigel A. Robins, *Eye of the Eagle: The Luftwaffe Aerial Photographs of Swansea*, 1st edn (Swansea: Tawe History, 1993), fig. 6.
- ⁴¹ Borough Engineer, Surveyor and Planning Officer's Department, sec. 2.
- ⁴² *Dealing With Dereliction: The Redevelopment of the Lower Swansea Valley*, ed. by Rosemary D. F. Bromley and Graham Humphrys (Swansea: University College of Swansea, 1979), pp. 186–87.
- ⁴³ Rosemary D. F. Bromley and Graham Humphrys, chaps 2 and 12.
- ⁴⁴ Stephen Hughes, p. 53.
- ⁴⁵ Louise Miskell, pp. 70–73.
- ⁴⁶ Nigel Robins, 'The Landscape History of Nyddfych (Penlle'rgaer)', *Minerva: The Swansea History Journal*, 29 (2021), 121–34.
- ⁴⁷ D. Trevor Williams, *The Economic Development of Swansea and of the Swansea District to 1921*, Social and Economic Survey of Swansea and District, 4 (Swansea: University of Wales Press Board, 1940); Chris Evans and Louise Miskell. Are good examples of influential works.
- ⁴⁸ 'Lle A Geo-Portal for Wales' <<https://lle.gov.wales/home?lang=en>> [accessed 1 December 2021].
- ⁴⁹ 'View Map: Glamorgan XXIV (Includes: Coed Ffranc; Swansea.) - Ordnance Survey Six-Inch England and Wales, 1842-1952' <<https://maps.nls.uk/view/102342508>> [accessed 1 December 2021]; 'View Map: Glamorgan XXIII.8 (Swansea) - Ordnance Survey 25 Inch England and Wales, 1841-1952' <<https://maps.nls.uk/view/135196942>> [accessed 1 December 2021].
- ⁵⁰ Nigel A. Robins, fig. 6,7.
- ⁵¹ 'Swansea Engl.Bl.26 GB4566', 1941, GX 11955 SG 008. Author's collection.
- ⁵² John R. Alban, *The Three Nights' Blitz: Select Contemporary Reports Relating to Swansea's Air Raids of February 1941*, Studies in Swansea's History (Swansea: City of Swansea, 1994), III, pp. 71–72.

⁵³ *The Lower Swansea Valley Project*, ed. by K. J. Hilton (London: Longmans, 1967).

⁵⁴ K.F. Broad, *Tree Planting on Man-Made Sites in Wales* (Forestry Commission, 1979), pp. 10, 25–26
<<https://www.forestresearch.gov.uk/documents/6846/FCOP003.pdf>> [accessed 23 September 2021].

⁵⁵ 'Historic LIDAR Archive' <<https://libcat.naturalresources.wales/folio/?oid=116826>> [accessed 1 December 2021].